

Effect of stearylamine on the physicochemical properties of liposomal formulations containing timolol maleate for ophthalmic application

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Abstract

Liposomes are widely investigated drug delivery systems because of their biocompatibility, ability to encapsulate hydrophilic and lipophilic compounds, and capacity to prolong drug release. In ophthalmic delivery, liposomes may improve drug retention on the ocular surface and reduce the rapid precorneal elimination associated with conventional eye drops. Such systems have attracted increasing interest as potential carriers for ocular drug delivery. Stearylamine is a positively charged lipid capable of modifying membrane properties and influencing interactions with negatively charged ocular structures. The aim of the present study was to develop and characterize liposomal formulations containing graded concentrations of stearylamine and to evaluate its effect on the physicochemical properties of liposomes containing timolol maleate. The formulations were characterized in terms of particle size, zeta potential, encapsulation efficiency, release profiles, and stability.

Keywords

Cholesterol, liposomal formulations, liposomes, phosphatidylcholine, physicochemical characterization, stearylamine

Introduction

Drug delivery to ocular tissues remains a significant challenge due to anatomical and physiological barriers that limit drug penetration and reduce therapeutic efficacy. Conventional ophthalmic dosage forms, such as eye drops, exhibit low bioavailability as a result of rapid tear turnover, blinking, and nasolacrimal drainage, leading to frequent administration and an increased risk of systemic side effects (Han et al. 2023; Al Yabhouni and Mozumder 2024). Glaucoma is a chronic ocular disease associated with elevated intraocular pressure and progressive optic nerve damage (Agarwal et al. 2016). Pharmacological treatment is primarily aimed at reducing intraocular pressure, commonly through β -ad-

renergic receptor blockers such as timolol maleate. However, conventional formulations of timolol maleate are associated with limited ocular residence time and potential systemic absorption (Dubey et al. 2015; Acharya et al. 2016). Liposomal drug delivery systems have been widely investigated as carriers for ophthalmic applications due to their biocompatibility, ability to encapsulate both hydrophilic and lipophilic substances, and structural similarity to biological membranes (Rania et al. 2007; Torres-Luna et al. 2020). Their physicochemical properties and stability are strongly dependent on membrane composition (Ibrahim et al. 2014). Phosphatidylcholine is commonly used as a structural lipid, while cholesterol is incorporated to regulate membrane rigidity and stability (Akbarzadeh et al.

2013; Gote et al. 2019). The incorporation of charge-inducing agents such as stearylamine represents an effective approach for modifying liposomal surface properties (Fathalla et al. 2015; El-Gendy and Mansour 2020). Stearylamine provides a positive surface charge, which enhances electrostatic repulsion between vesicles, improves colloidal stability, and promotes interactions with negatively charged ocular tissues, potentially increasing residence time (Dey et al. 2000; Soltan Monem et al. 2000). The aim of the present study was to prepare and characterize liposomal formulations composed of phosphatidylcholine and cholesterol, as well as formulations containing stearylamine at different concentrations (5, 10, and 15 mg), and to evaluate the influence of lipid composition on physicochemical properties and drug delivery performance.

Materials and methods

Materials

Soy phosphatidylcholine, cholesterol, stearylamine, oleic acid, timolol maleate, chloroform, methanol, potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4), and disodium hydrogen phosphate (Na_2HPO_4) were obtained from Sigma–Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). All chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade and used without further purification. Four formulations were prepared with the following compositions: phosphatidylcholine:cholesterol (200:15 mg) and phosphatidylcholine:cholesterol:stearylamine at ratios of 200:15:5 mg, 200:15:10 mg, and 200:15:15 mg.

Preparation of liposomal formulations

Liposomal formulations were prepared using the thin-lipid-film hydration method. The lipid components were dissolved in a chloroform–methanol mixture 2:1 (v/v). The solutions were prepared in 50 mL round-bottom flasks. The organic solvent was removed under reduced pressure at 40–45 °C and 400 mmHg for 2 h using a rotary evaporator, resulting in the formation of a thin lipid film on the inner walls of the flask. The obtained lipid film was hydrated with 20 mL phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) containing timolol maleate at a concentration of 0.1 mg/mL at 50–55 °C for 30 min under constant stirring at 100 rpm, leading to the formation of multilamellar vesicles (MLVs). Timolol maleate was incorporated by passive loading during the hydration step. The resulting liposomal dispersions were subjected to size reduction using an ultrasonic bath maintained at 40–45 °C. Sonication was performed in three cycles of 3 min each, with 1 min intervals between cycles to prevent excessive heating of the system.

Morphological characterization

The morphology of the prepared liposomal formulations was evaluated by light microscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM).

Preliminary morphological evaluation of the developed liposomal formulations was performed using light microscopy, particularly for visualization of MLVs present in the native dispersions. An aliquot of the freshly prepared liposomal dispersion was directly deposited onto a clean glass slide and covered with a coverslip to stabilize the sample during observation. The native liposomal dispersions were examined under direct observation using a Leica optical microscope equipped with Zeiss optics at $\times 400$ magnification. Observations were performed at room temperature immediately after preparation. Vesicle morphology, homogeneity, and the presence of visible aggregation were visually assessed, and representative micrographs were recorded. All investigated formulations, including the control formulation (PC:CH, 200:15 mg) and stearylamine-containing formulations (PC:CH:SA, 200:15:5 mg, 200:15:10 mg, and 200:15:15 mg), consisted of spherical vesicles uniformly distributed in the aqueous phase, without significant aggregation. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed for visualization of the developed liposomal formulations. Prior to analysis, liposomal dispersions were lyophilized using 5% (w/v) mannitol as a cryoprotectant. The dried samples were mounted and coated with a thin conductive gold layer under high vacuum to improve electrical conductivity. SEM micrographs were recorded at $\times 1,500$ magnification and an accelerating voltage of 15 kV using a scanning electron microscope (Hitachi TM 400). The obtained images were used to assess the presence of aggregation and the surface appearance of the liposomal systems. SEM images of lyophilized samples confirmed the presence of discrete particles with no significant aggregation. The results indicate the successful formation of liposomal vesicles with homogeneous morphology.

Particle size analysis

The particle size distribution and vesicle morphology of the developed liposomal formulations were evaluated using TEM and dynamic light scattering (DLS). Prior to TEM analysis, freshly prepared liposomal dispersions were diluted 1:10 with phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). An aliquot of each diluted sample was deposited onto a carbon-coated copper grid and allowed to dry under ambient conditions before imaging. No staining or freeze-treatment procedures were applied. TEM examination was performed using a JEOL JEM-2100 transmission electron microscope (JEOL Ltd., Japan) operated at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. Particle size measurements were performed from the obtained micrographs using ImageJ software (National Institutes of Health, USA). The diameters of 600 individual vesicles were manually measured to determine particle size distribution and mean vesicle size. The hydrodynamic particle size and polydispersity index (PDI) of the liposomal formulations were further determined by DLS using a Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Instruments, UK). For DLS analysis, liposomal dispersions were diluted 1:20 with phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) to reduce particle–particle interactions and minimize

multiple-scattering effects. Measurements were carried out using a quartz cuvette at 25 °C and a scattering angle of 90°. The Z-average hydrodynamic diameter and PDI values were recorded for each formulation. To evaluate formulation stability, hydrodynamic diameter and PDI were determined immediately after preparation (day 0) and after 30 days of storage at 4 ± 1 °C. All measurements were performed in triplicate ($n = 3$), and the results are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD).

Zeta potential determination

The surface charge of the developed liposomal formulations was evaluated by zeta potential analysis using a Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Instruments, UK). Prior to analysis, samples were diluted 1:20 with phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) to ensure appropriate measurement conditions. Measurements were carried out at 25 °C, and zeta potential values were recorded to assess the electrostatic stability of the liposomal systems. All analyses were performed in triplicate ($n = 3$).

Encapsulation efficiency determination

Encapsulation efficiency (EE%) was determined after separation of the non-encapsulated timolol maleate from the liposomal fraction by centrifugation. Briefly, 10 mL liposomal dispersions were centrifuged using a Beckman Coulter Avanti J-26 XP centrifuge (Beckman Coulter, USA) at 26,000 rpm for 90 min at 22 °C. Following centrifugation, the pellet containing the liposomal vesicles was removed, while the supernatant containing the non-encapsulated drug was carefully collected and analyzed by UV-Vis spectrophotometry at 292 nm. The concentration of timolol maleate was determined using a calibration curve prepared at the same wavelength. The amount of encapsulated timolol maleate was calculated indirectly as the difference between the initially added drug amount and the amount of free drug detected in the supernatant. Encapsulation efficiency was calculated according to the following equation:

$$EE(\%) = \frac{W_i - W_a}{W_i} \cdot 100$$

where W_i is the initial amount of drug used for liposome preparation and W_a is the amount of non-encapsulated drug determined in the aqueous phase after centrifugation.

In vitro drug release study

In vitro drug release of timolol maleate from the developed liposomal formulations was evaluated using the dialysis bag diffusion method. An aliquot (2 mL) of each liposomal dispersion was placed into a prehydrated dialysis membrane (molecular weight cutoff 12–14 kDa), which was sealed and immersed in 100 mL phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) serving as the release medium. The system was maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C under continuous magnetic stirring at 100 rpm. Samples (2 mL) were withdrawn at predetermined time intervals (15, 30, and 60 min and 2, 4, 6, 8, 12, and 24 h) and replaced

with an equal volume of fresh phosphate buffer to maintain constant volume and sink conditions. The concentration of timolol maleate was determined by UV-Vis spectrophotometry at 292 nm using a calibration curve prepared at the same wavelength. The cumulative drug release was calculated as a function of time. All experiments were performed in triplicate ($n = 3$), and the results are expressed as mean ± SD.

Release kinetic analysis

The release kinetics of timolol maleate from the developed liposomal formulations were evaluated by fitting the experimental *in vitro* release data to different mathematical models to characterize the release mechanism. The cumulative drug release data were analyzed according to zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas kinetic models using the following equations:

$$Q_t = Q_0 + k_0 \cdot t$$

$$\ln(100 - Q_t) = \ln 100 - k_1 t$$

$$Q_t = k_H t^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = k_{kP} \cdot t^n$$

where Q_t represents the cumulative amount of drug released at time t ; K_0 , K_1 , K_H , and K_{kP} are the corresponding kinetic constants; M_t/M_∞ is the fraction of drug released; and n is the diffusion exponent. The suitability of each model was evaluated based on the correlation coefficient (R^2).

Stability study

The physical stability of the developed liposomal formulations was evaluated over a 30-day storage period. Liposomal dispersions were stored at 4 ± 1 °C and protected from light. Stability assessment was performed at predetermined time intervals (day 0 and day 30). The formulations were evaluated for changes in macroscopic appearance, including visible aggregation, sedimentation, and phase separation. In addition, particle size distribution, PDI, pH, and EE% were monitored to assess physicochemical stability during storage. The ability of the dispersions to redisperse upon gentle shaking was also visually evaluated. All measurements were performed in triplicate ($n = 3$).

Statistical analysis

All experiments were performed in triplicate ($n = 3$), and the results are expressed as mean ± SD. Statistical analyses were performed using OriginPro software (OriginLab Corporation, USA). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's *post hoc* test was applied to compare EE% among formulations, while two-way ANOVA was used to evaluate the effects of formulation composition and storage time on EE%, particle size, and PDI. Statistical significance was accepted at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Morphological characterization

Representative light microscopy images of the developed liposomal formulations are presented in Fig. 1. Microscopic examination revealed the formation of MLVs with predominantly spherical morphology and broad size distribution, which is characteristic of liposomal systems prepared by the thin-lipid-film hydration method. Both the control and stearylamine-containing formulations showed homogeneous dispersion of vesicles throughout the aqueous phase, without visible aggregation or phase separation. No substantial morphological differences were observed between the investigated formulations at the optical microscopy level.

Particle size analysis

TEM analysis revealed nanosized vesicles with well-defined boundaries and relatively uniform size distribution, ranging from 150 to 590 nm for small unilamellar vesicles (SUVs). The control formulation (PC, 200:15 mg) showed particle sizes ranging from 45.58 to 590 nm, with a mean size of 127.06 ± 0.68 nm. Incorporation of stearylamine resulted in a gradual increase in particle size.

The formulation PC:CH (200:15:5 mg) exhibited sizes between 27.41 and 482.62 nm (mean 146.33 ± 0.97 nm), while PC:CH (200:15:10 mg) showed a range of 47.82–530 nm (mean 152.54 ± 0.83 nm). The formulation containing 15 mg stearylamine produced vesicles with sizes between 67.04 and 592.23 nm and a mean particle size of 178.50 ± 0.74 nm. DLS measurements performed during the stability study confirmed the nanoscale size distribution of the formulations. The Z-average values ranged from 241.2 to 327.3 nm at day 0 and from 326.4 to 374.8 nm after 30 days of storage. The PDI values remained below 0.35 for all samples, indicating a relatively narrow size distribution and acceptable colloidal homogeneity. A slight increase in particle size during storage was observed for all formulations.

Zeta potential

The control formulation (PC:CH, 200:15 mg) exhibited a slightly negative surface charge (-4.47 ± 0.64 mV). Incorporation of stearylamine resulted in a concentration-dependent increase in zeta potential. The formulation PC:CH:SA (200:15:5 mg) showed a value of 5.53 ± 0.48 mV, which increased to 12.47 ± 0.57 mV for PC:CH:SA (200:15:10 mg) and reached 16.53 ± 0.72 mV for PC:CH:SA (200:15:15 mg). The observed shift from negative to

Figure 1. Representative light microscopy images of the developed liposomal formulations: A. Control formulation (PC:CH, 200:15 mg); B. Stearylamine-containing formulation (PC:CH:SA, 200:15:15 mg).

Figure 2. Representative TEM images of liposomal vesicles: A. Control formulation (PC:CH, 200:15 mg); B. Stearylamine-containing formulation (PC:CH:SA, 200:15:15 mg).

Figure 3. SEM images of liposomal formulations: **A.** Control formulation composed of phosphatidylcholine and cholesterol (PC:CH, 200:15 mg); **B.** Stearylamine-containing formulation (PC:CH:SA, 200:15:15 mg).

Figure 4. Particle size distribution of liposomal formulations determined by image analysis: **A.** Control formulation (PC:CH, 200:15 mg); **B.** Stearylamine-containing formulation (PC:CH:SA, 200:15:5 mg); **C.** Stearylamine-containing formulation (PC:CH:SA, 200:15:10 mg); **D.** Stearylamine-containing formulation (PC:CH:SA, 200:15:15 mg).

positive values confirmed the successful incorporation of stearylamine and indicates enhanced electrostatic stabilization of the liposomal dispersions.

Encapsulation efficiency

The EE% values ranged from 55.7% to 65.1%, depending on the lipid composition. The control formulation (PC:CH, 200:15 mg) showed an EE% of $55.7 \pm 2.1\%$. Incorporation of stearylamine resulted in a gradual increase in EE%. The formulation PC:CH:SA (200:15:5 mg) exhibited an EE% of $58.6 \pm 2.0\%$, while PC:CH:SA (200:15:10 mg) showed

an EE% of $61.8 \pm 2.3\%$. The highest EE% was observed for PC:CH:SA (200:15:15 mg), reaching $65.1 \pm 2.5\%$. The results indicate that increasing stearylamine content enhances drug retention within the liposomal vesicles.

Table 1. EE% of timolol maleate in liposomal formulations.

Formulation	EE (%)
PC:CH (200:15)	54.55 ± 0.37^a
PC:CH:SA (200:15:5 mg)	57.86 ± 0.32^b
PC:CH:SA (200:15:10 mg)	59.18 ± 0.44^c
PC:CH:SA (200:15:15 mg)	62.49 ± 0.39^d

Figure 5. *In vitro* release profiles of timolol maleate from liposomal formulations over 24 h: **A.** Control formulation (PC:CH, 200:15 mg); **B.** Stearylamine-containing formulations: PC:CH:SA (200:15:5 mg), PC:CH:SA (200:15:10 mg), and PC:CH:SA (200:15:15 mg).

Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's *post hoc* test. Different superscript letters indicate statistically significant differences among formulations ($p < 0.05$). One-way ANOVA revealed significant differences among the investigated formulations ($F(3, 8) = 230.06, p < 0.0001$). The release of timolol maleate from the developed liposomal formulations exhibited a gradual and sustained profile over 24 h. The control formulation (PC:CH 200:15 mg) showed a relatively faster release rate, reaching approximately 50% within the first hour and approximately 92% after 24 h. Incorporation of stearylamine resulted in a concentration-dependent prolongation of drug release. The formulations PC:CH:SA (200:15:5 mg), PC:CH:SA (200:15:10 mg), and PC:CH:SA (200:15:15 mg) demonstrated reduced release rates during the initial phase, with approximately 48%, 45%, and 42% release at 1 h, respectively. At 24 h, cumulative release values were approximately 91%, 90%, and 89%, respectively. The differences among formulations were most pronounced during the early time intervals (up to 8 h), where increasing stearylamine content led to a progressively slower release. After this period, the release profiles gradually approached a plateau.

Release kinetics

The kinetic analysis demonstrated that the release of timolol maleate from all liposomal formulations did not follow zero-order kinetics, as indicated by the low correlation coefficients ($R^2 = 0.550$ – 0.705). In contrast, the first-order model showed the highest correlation values ($R^2 = 0.969$ – 0.973), suggesting that drug release is concentration-dependent. The Higuchi model also demonstrated good correlation ($R^2 = 0.817$ – 0.924), indicating that diffusion through the lipid bilayer plays a significant role in controlling drug release. Further analysis using the Korsmeyer–Peppas model revealed diffusion exponent values ($n = 0.539$ – 0.660), corresponding to a non-Fickian transport mechanism.

Table 2. Kinetic parameters describing the release of timolol maleate from the control liposomal formulation PC:CH (200:15 mg).

Kinetic model	Parameter	Value
Zero-order model	K_0	3.411
	R^2	0.550
First-order model	K_1	0.258
	R^2	0.969
Higuchi model	K_h	19.798
	R^2	0.817
Korsmeyer-Peppas model	KKP	0.480
	n	0.539
	R^2	0.944

Stability of liposomal formulations during storage

The majority of particles remained within the range of 450–700 nm, with no formation of large aggregates. DLS measurements (Table 4) showed a moderate increase in Z-average values after 30 days, while PDI remained below 0.35 for all formulations, indicating acceptable colloidal homogeneity. The pH values remained stable during storage, with variations within ± 0.1 units (7.2–7.5), suggesting no significant degradation of lipid components. EE% decreased gradually over time for all formulations. The control formulation (PC:CH 200:15 mg) showed a decrease from 56.55% to 31.22% after 30 days. Formulations containing stearylamine exhibited improved drug retention, with final EE% values of 27.54%, 32.08%, and 35.99% for PC:CH:SA 200:15:5 mg, 200:15:10 mg, and 200:15:15 mg, respectively.

Particle size and PDI values of the developed liposomal formulations at day 0 and after 30 days of storage are presented in Table 4. An increase in Z-average values was observed for all formulations during storage, indicating changes in vesicle size over time. Similarly, PDI values increased after 30 days of storage, suggesting a broader particle size distribution. Two-way ANOVA demonstrated significant effects of formulation composition

Table 3. Kinetic parameters of timolol maleate release from liposomal formulations containing different concentrations of stearylamine.

Kinetic model	Parameter	PC:CH:SA (200:15:5 mg)	PC:CH:SA (200:15:10 mg)	PC:CH:SA (200:15:15 mg)
Zero-order model	K_0	3.599	3.611	3.620
	R^2	0.625	0.659	0.705
First-order model	K_1	0.211	0.188	0.169
	R^2	0.972	0.969	0.973
Higuchi model	K_h	20.251	20.039	19.727
	R^2	0.873	0.895	0.924
Korsmeyer-Peppas model	KKP	0.409	0.378	0.345
	n	0.609	0.642	0.660
	R^2	0.932	0.927	0.916

Table 4. Particle size (Z-average) and PDI of liposomal formulations at day 0 and after 30 days of storage.

Formulation	Day 0	Day 0	Day 30	Day 30
Parameter	PDI	Z-average (nm)	PDI	Z-average (nm)
PC:CH (200:15 mg)	0.193 ± 0.007	241.2 ± 4.2	0.221 ± 0.007	326.4 ± 8.5
PC:CH:SA (200:15:5 mg)	0.251 ± 0.007	327.3 ± 7.7	0.306 ± 0.009	341.6 ± 8.4
PC:CH:SA (200:15:10 mg)	0.219 ± 0.009	326.3 ± 8.5	0.284 ± 0.008	374.8 ± 8.8
PC:CH:SA (200:15:15 mg)	0.262 ± 0.008	319.4 ± 8.0	0.305 ± 0.011	361.5 ± 9.4

($F = 81.71$, $p < 0.0001$), storage time ($F = 208.40$, $p < 0.0001$), and their interaction ($F = 19.64$, $p < 0.0001$) on particle size. Significant effects of formulation composition ($F = 109.26$, $p < 0.0001$), storage time ($F = 203.05$, $p < 0.0001$), and their interaction ($F = 5.66$, $p = 0.0077$) were also observed for PDI values. Despite these changes, all formulations remained within the nanometer size range and maintained PDI values below 0.35 throughout the storage period. Among the investigated formula-

tions, PC:CH:SA (200:15:15 mg) demonstrated the most favorable overall stability profile, exhibiting the highest EE% after 30 days of storage while maintaining acceptable particle size and PDI value.

Data are presented as mean ± SD ($n = 3$). Statistical analysis was performed using two-way ANOVA. Significant effects of formulation composition ($F = 484.03$, $p < 0.0001$), storage time ($F = 37168.99$, $p < 0.0001$), and their interaction ($F = 106.03$, $p < 0.0001$) were observed.

Figure 6. Changes in particle size distribution of liposomal formulations during storage as determined by DLS: A. Control formulation (PC:CH, 200:15 mg); B. Formulation containing stearylamine (PC:CH:SA, 200:15:5 mg); C. Formulation containing stearylamine (PC:CH:SA, 200:15:10 mg); D. Formulation containing stearylamine (PC:CH:SA, 200:15:15 mg).

Figure 7. Macroscopic appearance of selected liposomal formulations before and after storage at 4 ± 1 °C (day 0 and day 30): **A.** Control formulation (PC:CH, 200:15 mg) at day 0; **B.** Control formulation after 30 days of storage; **C.** Stearylamine-containing formulation (PC:CH:SA, 200:15:15 mg) at day 0; **D.** Stearylamine-containing formulation after 30 days of storage.

Table 5. EE% of timolol maleate in the developed liposomal formulations at day 0 and after 30 days of storage.

Formulation	EE (%) day 0	EE (%) day 30
PC:CH (200:15)	54.55 ± 0.37	31.22 ± 0.23
PC:CH:SA (200:15:5)	57.86 ± 0.32	27.54 ± 0.27
PC:CH:SA (200:15:10)	59.18 ± 0.44	32.08 ± 0.31
PC:CH:SA (200:15:15)	62.49 ± 0.39	35.99 ± 0.33

Discussion

The principal structural components used in the development of the liposomal systems in the present study were phosphatidylcholine, cholesterol, and stearylamine, the latter being incorporated at graded concentrations (5, 10, and 15 mg). The liposomal dispersions were prepared in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), providing an environment close to physiological ocular conditions. The selection of these components was based on previous literature reports describing their frequent use in the development of ophthalmic nanosystems, owing to their favorable biocompatibility, biodegradability, and low toxicity profile, which are essential requirements for ocular drug delivery systems (Valcarcel et al. 2001; Levchenko et al. 2002). Timolol maleate was selected as a model drug due to its widespread clinical application in the treatment of glaucoma and ocular hypertension, as well as the limitations associated with conventional ophthalmic formulations, including short

ocular residence time and low bioavailability. Furthermore, the hydrophilic nature of timolol maleate makes it a suitable candidate for incorporation into the aqueous core of liposomal vesicles. From a physicochemical perspective, phosphatidylcholine plays a critical role in liposome formation due to its amphiphilic structure, consisting of a hydrophilic phosphocholine head group and hydrophobic fatty acid chains. This molecular organization enables spontaneous self-assembly into bilayer vesicles in aqueous environments, driven by hydrophobic interactions and minimization of interfacial free energy. Due to its structural similarity to biological membranes, phosphatidylcholine is among the most commonly used phospholipids in liposomal formulations. In the present system, phosphatidylcholine provided the structural basis for vesicle formation and enabled effective incorporation of hydrophilic timolol maleate into the aqueous core of the liposomes (Torchilin 2005; Natarajan et al. 2011). The EE% of timolol maleate was significantly influenced by the incorporation of stearylamine into the liposomal bilayer. The control formulation (PC:CH, 200:15 mg) exhibited an EE% of $54.55 \pm 0.37\%$, whereas the addition of stearylamine resulted in a progressive increase in drug entrapment, reaching $57.86 \pm 0.33\%$, $59.18 \pm 0.45\%$, and $62.49 \pm 0.36\%$ for formulations containing 5, 10, and 15 mg of stearylamine, respectively. One-way ANOVA revealed statistically significant differences among the investigated formulations ($F = 230.06$, $p < 0.001$). Subsequent Tukey's

post hoc analysis demonstrated that each formulation differed significantly from all other formulations ($p < 0.05$), as indicated by the distinct superscript letters assigned to the mean values. These findings suggest that increasing stearylamine concentration enhances the EE% of timolol maleate, most likely due to improved bilayer organization and stronger interactions between the positively charged stearylamine molecules and the lipid membrane, which reduce drug leakage during liposome preparation. Electrostatic interactions between timolol maleate and phosphatidylcholine head groups may contribute to improved drug retention within the liposomal structure, even in the absence of a charge-inducing agent (Afouna et al. 2008; Shafaa et al. 2011). Cholesterol represents another essential component of the developed system, contributing to membrane rigidity, bilayer organization, and overall vesicle stability. Previous studies have demonstrated that cholesterol reduces membrane fluidity and permeability, thereby limiting premature drug leakage and improving structural integrity. However, excessive cholesterol concentrations may result in highly rigid membrane structures that could compromise drug loading efficiency. The results obtained in the present study suggest that the selected phosphatidylcholine-to-cholesterol ratio provided a favorable balance between membrane stability and EE%, as demonstrated by successful vesicle formation and satisfactory drug loading. Initial observation of freshly prepared liposomal dispersions using light microscopy revealed a heterogeneous particle population with broad size distribution, including vesicles exceeding 1 μm , which is characteristic of MLVs formed by thin-lipid-film hydration methods. Following ultrasonic size reduction, particle dimensions decreased considerably and shifted toward a size interval more appropriate for ophthalmic drug delivery (Cristiano et al. 2021; Song et al. 2022). TEM analysis confirmed the successful formation of liposomal vesicles with predominantly spherical morphology and relatively homogeneous structural organization. The mean particle size gradually increased with increasing stearylamine concentration, ranging from 127.06 ± 0.68 nm for the control formulation to 146.33 ± 0.97 nm, 152.54 ± 0.83 nm, and 178.50 ± 0.74 nm for formulations containing 5, 10, and 15 mg stearylamine, respectively. A similar tendency was observed in the DLS measurements, where the hydrodynamic diameter (Z-average) ranged from 241.2 to 327.3 nm at day 0. The larger particle size values obtained by DLS compared with TEM are expected and can be explained by methodological differences between the techniques. The gradual increase in particle size following stearylamine incorporation may be attributed to changes in lipid packing within the phospholipid bilayer. Owing to its long hydrophobic chain and protonated amino group, stearylamine may influence membrane organization and steric interactions, resulting in moderate vesicle enlargement. Similar observations have been reported in liposomal systems containing cationic lipids, where positively charged membrane modifiers affect vesicle size and colloidal organization. Despite the observed size increase, the

formulations maintained acceptable colloidal homogeneity, as demonstrated by PDI values below 0.35 for all systems throughout the stability period. Two-way ANOVA demonstrated significant effects of formulation composition, storage time, and their interaction on both particle size and PDI values ($p < 0.05$). Although an increase in particle size and PDI was observed after 30 days of storage, all formulations remained within the nanometer range and maintained acceptable colloidal characteristics. At the same time, a gradual reduction in encapsulated drug content was observed during the 30-day stability study, indicating that drug leakage may occur independently of major structural destabilization or particle aggregation. This observation suggests that the decrease in EE% may be associated with subtle structural rearrangements within the lipid bilayer rather than complete vesicle disruption (Sercombe et al. 2015; Large et al. 2021). The EE% of all liposomal formulations decreased after 30 days of storage, indicating gradual drug leakage from the vesicular systems over time. However, the extent of this reduction depended on the formulation composition. The formulation containing 15 mg stearylamine retained the highest EE% after storage ($35.99 \pm 0.33\%$), whereas the formulation containing 5 mg stearylamine exhibited the lowest value ($27.54 \pm 0.27\%$). Two-way ANOVA revealed significant effects of formulation composition, storage time, and their interaction on EE% ($p < 0.0001$). These findings indicate that the influence of storage on drug retention was dependent on stearylamine concentration. The improved retention observed at higher stearylamine concentrations suggests enhanced membrane stabilization, which may reduce bilayer permeability and contribute to more efficient retention of timolol maleate within the liposomal vesicles during storage. The release profiles of timolol maleate from the developed liposomal formulations demonstrated a biphasic release pattern, characterized by an initial rapid release phase followed by a slower and more sustained release over time. The control formulation (PC:CH 200:15 mg) exhibited the fastest release rate, reaching approximately 50% cumulative drug release within the first hour. Incorporation of stearylamine resulted in a concentration-dependent reduction in the initial release rate, with the formulation containing the highest stearylamine concentration (PC:CH:SA 200:15:15 mg) exhibiting the lowest release during the first hour (approximately 42%). This observation suggests that stearylamine affects the structural organization of the lipid bilayer, reduces membrane permeability, and limits timolol maleate diffusion during the initial phase of release. Stearylamine appears to play a key role within the liposomal membrane in terms of both drug retention within the vesicles and the subsequent release processes. This observation is consistent with the findings reported by Webb et al. (2015), further supporting the contribution of stearylamine to modulation of liposomal drug release behavior. Despite the differences observed in the early stages, all formulations reached high cumulative release values after 24 h (approximately 89–92%), indicating that stearylamine does not prevent drug

release but rather modulates and prolongs it over time. The most pronounced differences between formulations were observed during the first hours of the release study, whereas the release profiles gradually converged at later time points. The observed initial rapid release phase (burst effect) may be attributed to the localization of a fraction of timolol maleate molecules near the liposomal surface, influenced by the presence of stearylamine within the lipid bilayer. At pH 7.4, the protonated amino group of stearylamine may alter the spatial distribution of ionized timolol maleate, resulting in preferential positioning of a portion of the drug molecules within the peripheral regions of the vesicles, where they are more readily available for diffusion. This may explain the release of approximately 42–50% of the drug during the first hour. The gradual slowing of drug release at later stages suggests that the remaining fraction of timolol maleate is predominantly retained within the hydrophilic compartments of the liposomes, from which it is released more slowly through diffusion across the lipid bilayer. The increasing stearylamine concentration and the corresponding reduction in the intensity of the burst effect indicate that stearylamine likely promotes reorganization and compaction of the lipid membrane, thereby contributing to the prolonged release profile observed up to 24 h (Sainaga Jyothi et al. 2022). The kinetic analysis further confirmed that the release of timolol maleate from the liposomal formulations represents a complex process governed by both drug concentration and diffusion through the lipid bilayer. The relatively low correlation coefficients observed for the zero-order model indicate that drug release did not occur at a constant rate. In contrast, the first-order model exhibited the highest correlation coefficients ($R^2 = 0.969–0.973$), indicating a concentration-dependent release mechanism, which is consistent with the experimentally observed biphasic release profile. Consistent with the findings of Mourtas et al. (2007), the results of the present study further confirm that the biopharmaceutical properties of the drug molecule, particularly lipophilicity, play an important role in determining its release behavior from the matrix system of the dosage form. The satisfactory correlation with the Higuchi model further supports the significant contribution of diffusion-controlled processes to drug release. Moreover, the diffusion exponent ($n = 0.539–0.660$) obtained from the Korsmeyer–Peppas model suggests a non-Fickian transport mechanism, involving both diffusion and structural reorganization of the lipid membrane. Importantly, the gradual decrease in the first-order release constant (k_1) with increasing stearylamine concentration indicates that stearylamine slows drug release in a concentration-dependent manner, most likely through increased bilayer compactness and reduced membrane permeability (Figueiredo et al. 2012). From a therapeutic perspective, the observed biphasic release behavior may be advantageous for ophthalmic drug delivery, as it allows rapid achievement of initial therapeutic concentrations, followed by a prolonged release phase that could potentially reduce dosing frequency and improve patient

compliance. Previous studies have emphasized the critical importance of both the physicochemical properties of the drug molecule and the surrounding environment in determining liposomal system behavior and stability (Puranik et al. 2012). When interpreting the findings of the present study in the context of ophthalmic administration, it becomes evident that the ability of liposomal particles to provide prolonged drug release is a key factor for improving ocular drug delivery performance. The stability results suggest that stearylamine plays a multifunctional role in the physicochemical stabilization of liposomal systems, extending beyond its function as a charge-inducing lipid. The gradual increase in positive surface charge, together with the absence of irreversible aggregation and the maintenance of PDI values below 0.35, indicates improved colloidal stability through electrostatic repulsion between vesicles. Notably, although a moderate increase in particle size was observed during storage, the vesicular systems retained their overall structural integrity and redispersibility, suggesting preservation of liposomal organization. Previous authors have emphasized the critical importance of each formulation parameter in liposome development and the maintenance of system stability (Song et al. 2021). The findings obtained in the present study further support and confirm these observations. Importantly, the observed decrease in EE% during storage despite relatively preserved particle size suggests that vesicle integrity and drug retention are not fully equivalent processes. While stearylamine appears to contribute to maintaining structural stability, gradual drug leakage likely occurs through subtle membrane rearrangements rather than complete vesicle destabilization. The higher residual drug content observed in formulations containing increased stearylamine concentrations further indicates a concentration-dependent membrane-stabilizing effect, supporting the role of stearylamine as a membrane-modulating excipient capable of improving prolonged drug retention and sustained release behavior. Overall, the obtained findings demonstrate that stearylamine plays a significant role in modulating the physicochemical behavior of timolol maleate-loaded liposomes, influencing vesicle organization, drug retention, release behavior, and colloidal stability in a concentration-dependent manner. Although gradual drug leakage was observed during storage, the developed systems maintained their structural integrity and satisfactory physicochemical characteristics throughout the investigated period. These findings contribute to a better understanding of the role of stearylamine in modulating the properties of liposomal systems.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrates that liposomal formulations based on phosphatidylcholine and cholesterol can be successfully developed and further optimized through incorporation of stearylamine. The inclusion of stearylamine enhanced membrane organization, reduced permeability,

and contributed to improved drug retention and colloidal stability. Kinetic analysis confirmed that drug release is primarily diffusion-controlled and follows first-order kinetics with a non-Fickian mechanism. The results obtained in this study demonstrate that stearylamine

plays a key role in modulating the physicochemical properties and performance of timolol maleate-loaded liposomal formulations, highlighting the importance of lipid composition in the design and optimization of liposomal drug delivery systems.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

Regarding the use of AI in the preparation of this manuscript, the authors declare the following: GPT.

Used for: Language, style and writing.

AI-assisted tools were used solely for language editing, stylistic improvement, and clarity of expression. All scientific content, data analysis, and interpretations are the author's own.

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Author contributions

R. K. conceived the study, designed the experiments, performed the experiments, analyzed the data, and wrote the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.
